

University Language Programs And Skills In The Craft Sector: Transversality And Decompartmentalization

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Abstract

This research started from the idea of bringing language training closer to the socio-professional environment through a case study in the artisanal field. This alignment was considered based on the identification of transversal skills that could ensure the breaking down of the questioned training. Given this objective, the starting point is the main assumption that the transfer of skills from training to professional environments and vice versa is only possible through the identification of core competencies through an association between formalised knowledge (theoretical, procedural, and cognitive) and action-based knowledge (procedural, experiential, environmental, etc.) within the framework of situated and reflective learning devices. The verification of this hypothesis required the use of a grid of six transversal skills (mobilization/integration, transfer/adaptability, reflexivity/systematization, progressive.

construction/contextualization, co-professionalization/co-construction, social and civic purposes) within the framework of a qualitative content analysis of the French degree and the nomenclature of artisanal activities and trades. The main results show the emergence of core transversal skills related to communication/mediation, planning and organisation, analysis and diagnosis, reflexivity and regulation, and adaptability and contextualisation. Areas of decompartmentalization as well as gaps were also highlighted by the grid of the six transversal axes. It highlights the unequal nature of transferability depending on the professions (variable weight of standards, technicality, and environments) and according to pedagogical conditions (partnerships, task scripting, support, and aligned evaluation).

Keywords: skills transversalization; professionalization; activity analysis; craftsmanship; French degree programme

1. INTRODUCTION

The transversality of skills is a notable feature of the international and national university system under the influence of a knowledge economy that currently impacts all sectors of society within the framework of an “intellectualisation of production” (Bouchez, 2014, p.13). The intellectualisation of production implies closer relationships between research, education, and production, which concretely manifest as an “intellectual investment” (Caspar, cited by Bouchez, 2014, p.13) consisting of introducing intelligence into the professional world and more specifically into the world of work.

This articulation between intelligence and the world of production inevitably involves a transposition of skills acquired within the framework of initial or continuous training towards economic sectors that not only work in favour of successful professional integration of graduates but also aspire to a real use of these skills in complex and varied professional situations as well as their continuous development. Nevertheless, this transfer and effective use of skills are not always evident given the equation to solve between education and employment. Indeed, university programs are largely dependent on the

objectives assigned to them as well as the disciplinary requirements that are not necessarily in perfect harmony with the needs of the job market.

That is why this harmonisation can only be achieved by underpinning training programs with theoretical principles that acknowledge the pragmatic, contextual, and evolving nature of skills (Le Boterf, 2018). Other principles related to these same skills as a process of mobilising different resources according to the situations faced by students can also be taken into consideration, ensuring their transfer through a learning process of decontextualisation and recontextualization (Coulet, 2011).

In professional settings, this learning falls within the framework, according to Pastré (1999), of a “conceptualisation” in action (p.111) that considers professional activity as a training space in itself where knowledge is reconstructed according to the situation to be resolved. Considered as such, professional skills are situated at the level of a cycle where the process of their updating is iterative and intrinsically nourished within the framework of the workplace and extrinsically within the framework of university training. These are now at the heart of this theoretical and social debate and are required to follow this updating movement in light of the evolution of the job market.

For an understanding of this evolution in light of organising texts and within the framework of a case study, the observation of the craft sector lends itself better due to the availability of texts that govern it (The Algerian Nomenclature of Activities, established by the National Statistics Office (2009) and the Nomenclature of Craft Activities and Trades, carried out by the Ministry of Small and Medium Enterprises and Crafts in 2007) as well as due to the diversity and richness of the skills required by this sector. The guiding thread of this observation is the possibility of identifying cross-cutting themes through an articulation between language training skills and those of the crafts sector.

The examination of this relationship takes place within the framework of a hypothesis that assumes that the analysis of activity as envisioned by Minet (1999) allows for the identification of cross-cutting themes through “cores of competencies” that encompass two types of knowledge: formalised knowledge (theoretical and procedural) and “knowledge of action” (practical and know-how) (Pastré, 1999). These knowledge only make sense within the framework of a process that witnesses their mobilisation as well as their transformation. In this case, the knowledge within the context of university education is no longer arranged successively, but it is related in order to grasp its connection with transferable skills in the field of craftsmanship. This intelligibility is achieved through a pedagogical framework based on the theoretical background of “the conceptualisation of action” (Pastré, 1999; Malglaive, 1990), which will ensure the articulation between language training and artisanal skills through the competencies developed within university programs (communication, intercultural, disciplinary, methodological, etc.) and in the context of real artisanal situations.

By adhering to this assumption, the goal pursued is to break down the barriers between university programs to open them up to economic sectors through interprofessional and cross-disciplinary teaching, which should enable socio-economic innovation and sustainable development.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Competence in a professional context

2.1.1. Adynamic definition of competence

Competence in the context of activity analysis is not limited to a repertoire of held knowledge. According to the professional competence model as conceptualised by Minet (1995), it is a dynamic structure of abilities actualised in action, in continuous interaction

with the situation. In this regard, this model highlights the importance of specific skill sets relevant to any professional context, which include two categories of knowledge: formalised knowledge – theoretical and procedural, and action knowledge – practical, experiential.

The knowledge that can be relevantly mobilised in action can be broken down into several items: on one hand, the theoretical or procedural references from initial or continuous training that will constitute our formalised knowledge; on the other hand, the knowledge of action, which is experientially grounded, reflecting practical, situated intelligence, built through confrontation with the realities of the field.

Situational mobilisation, on the other hand, refers to the ability to adjust this knowledge to the complexity and variability of real situations. The transformation of activity refers to the evolution of skills through reflective feedback initiated by practice. Finally, the core contextual skills allow for thinking about the articulation between training and the field of application – here, craftsmanship – by promoting a contextualised reading of competence.

2.1.2. Conceptualisation in action

In line with these situated approaches, Pastré (1999) introduced the notion of conceptualisation in action, suggesting that the act of competence is not a simple mechanical application of knowledge. The learner builds their skills by conceptualising their actions, that is, by slowly appropriating operational invariants – in other words, stable structures that are identified in increasingly numerous and varied situations that guide action and are thus reactivated in context.

Thus, five key dimensions emerge from this conception:

- the mobilisation of operational invariants, the key to mastering similar situations through new configurations;
- the construction of an operational model specific to each individual, which allows for giving meaning to action through the development of internal representations based on experience;
- the verbal dimension of action, central to reflective development, which allows the learner to justify the reasoning underlying decision-making;
- the implementation of transfer between situations, reflecting the balance of constructed schemas;
- and finally, the determining role of the training system, whose quality of mediations it offers – tutoring, simulations, role-playing – is crucial in the emergence of these conceptualisation processes.

2.1.3. Formalised knowledge and action-based knowledge as levers for transversality

Articulating formalised knowledge and practical knowledge is essential to bridge the gap between educational environments and professional spheres within the framework of transversality, so highly advocated by the professionalisation of training. This is perfectly manifested in the context of the crafts sector - the subject of our analysis -, where the resolution of tangible problems, reflexivity, and underlying knowledge are of paramount importance.

The circulation of these elements in professional environments paves the way for a definition of competence (Le Boterf, 2018) as an integrated mobilisation of resources (knowledge, skills, attitude, etc.) in varied and complex professional situations.

Given this complex nature of competence, it is essential, for efficient mobilisation, to have a professional focus, to call upon reflexivity, as well as to take into account the situational nature of competence. In the context of this definition of professional competence, training programs are led to organise content according to an integrative process that fully aligns with action-based learning. In light of these foundations, competence is built in the wake of activity through a dialogic and constant interaction between action, conceptualisation, and interpretation, thereby moving away from its prescriptive conception.

Such a conception of competence requires the establishment of cross-cutting and de-compartmentalized training mechanisms with the major challenge of bringing university

training closer to real situations and the challenges of local and territorial development.

2.2. Competence in the university environment

2.2.1. University approaches to competence

Contrary to the conception stipulating that competence consists solely of mobilising disciplinary knowledge, new approaches consider it as an integrative and evolving process of academic, methodological, and experiential knowledge within the framework of diverse learning paths and contexts (Coulet, 2011). This new globalising vision of competence confers upon it, within the framework of the learning process, a progressive acquisition structure that operates from the initiation level to the mastery level according to a timeline that is specific to the training cycle. It also attributes to it the characteristic of the ability to integrate as a guarantee of mobilisation and articulation by students of disciplinary, linguistic, and professional knowledge in situations described as contextualised, complex, and significant.

This integration capacity is the central indicator of the possibility of transferring skills to professional environments, which requires a training engineering primarily articulated around the coherence of teaching units. This curricular coherence (horizontal and vertical) is at the heart of the pedagogical continuity process, which articulates between theoretical knowledge and practical knowledge to ensure the transfer of skills outside the university context.

These key principles of the program-based approach (Coulet and Loisy, 2018) are implemented through pedagogical devices mutually constructed in close collaboration between education professionals and those from the business world with the aim of breaking down the barriers of university education and consolidating interdisciplinarity. Placing the training at the crossroads of various disciplinary knowledge works in favour of acquiring complex skills that can be reused in common projects and in favour of professional integration and innovation.

2.3. Limits and challenges of competence

Despite the success that the notion of competence has in the academic context, it is the subject of several controversies led by several researchers, notably Rey (2015), who emphasises the tensions caused by its polysemous nature. Variable depending on the contexts (academic, professional, and social), the different understandings of competence draw two opposing divisions: for the first categorisation, it is assimilated to the acquisition of theoretical knowledge only, while for the second, it is considered as an implementation in action situations.

These oppositions bring to light a debate on the mission of the university: would it be merely a place for the transmission of knowledge, or is it an educational institution that concerns itself with their practical application in professional contexts? The answer to this question requires prior epistemological and political reflection on competence as a model that aligns with the socio-economic needs of society. Achieving the development of a competency model cannot be done without reflecting on the evaluation and regulatory mechanisms that have a direct impact on learning and pedagogical practices.

For an objective alignment of assessment with teaching-learning, it is essential to identify the purposes of assessment and translate them into terms of criteria, assessment object, methods, etc., in order to grasp from the outset the challenges and political and social issues of this assessment in a context of partiality of competency frameworks (Rey, 2015). Faced with the biased visions of these frameworks, we must not forget the type of citizen that the university wants to form with competency-based approaches (Rey, 2015) by analysing whether or not these approaches take into account critical thinking, civic engagement, and intellectual emancipation.

2.4. The breaking down of silos and the transversality of training: towards an engineering of professionalisation

2.4.1. The engineering of professionalisation

Fernagu-Oudet (2004) envisions a definition of professionalisation engineering at the intersection of the worlds of work and academia through the co-construction of training programs that overlap with the needs of professional spheres. The principles that underpin it fall within the framework of cross-professionalization, which follows a systemic approach that integrates skills from “vague and ordered” experience (2004, p.123), the prescriptions of the professional framework, and the objectives of university training.

These trainings within the framework of this type of engineering are constantly updated in their pedagogical approaches to make them more operational and transferable. The assurance of this transferability of skills from academic training is carried out within the framework of partnerships between academic stakeholders and professional stakeholders for better intelligibility of the process of mobilising skills in real-life situations and for the consideration of authentic situations in the design of pedagogical frameworks. This will greatly increase the transferability of skills in professional settings and establish professionalisation as a strategic lever for personal development, professional integration, and civic responsibility.

2.4.2. The program approach for disciplinary decompartmentalization

In the same perspective as the engineering of professionalisation, the program approach (Coulet and Loisy, 2018) presents itself as an approach that aims to break down disciplinary knowledge within a logic of strengthening transversality within the framework of structuring training around transversal skills, defined not at the level of the isolated teaching unit but at the program level. This program, within the framework of this approach, is based on four fundamental principles: the co-construction of the training offer, interdisciplinarity, curricular coherence (program logic), and pedagogical continuity between teaching units (Coulet and Loisy, 2018).

2.4.3. An integrative approach to transversality: between training, employability, and living together

In the same perspective of establishing a model related to transversality between academic and professional environments (procedural and action-oriented knowledge, co-construction and coherence of training, interdisciplinarity, pedagogical continuity) (Minet, 1999; Pastré, 1999; Fernagu-Oudet, 2004), Gendron (2019), according to an integrative approach, extends the training-employment continuum towards “living together” (p.) as an ethical dimension related to social inclusion and collective development. Beyond its technical and pragmatic nature, competence also covers emotional and behavioural aspects that allow for the construction of significant emotional capital for professional integration (Gendron, 2019). In addition to this professional integration, contributing to the construction of a supportive and democratic society is also the aim of a training engineering that aligns with an ethical and political perspective. According to this perspective, university programs are required to develop skills that allow for socialisation in terms of adapting to unstable environments, collaborating with actors from diverse backgrounds, and committing to collective projects. Sticking to these skills, the civic and intercultural dimension is at the heart of a cross-cutting approach with a civic and intercultural dimension.

2.5. Dynamics of competence, transversality process, and disciplinary decompartmentalization

Drawing on the theoretical elements previously mobilised, which refer to competence in professional and academic environments as well as transversality in the wake of professionalisation engineering, a systemic relationship emerges that establishes a true

dynamic of competence. **Figure No1** represents this relationship by organising four poles - academic competence, professional competence, transversality process, and disciplinary decompartmentalization - in a logic of permanent interactions where each feeds and transforms the other and the orientation of training towards integrated professionalisation. This integration is initially ensured by a process of transversality (Gendron, 2019; Fernagu-Oudet, 2004) that articulates knowledge, purposes, and social values through authentic learning situations and the development of reflexivity and the learners' identity.

In this context, skills in academic (Rey, 2015; Coulet, 2011) and professional (Minet, 1999; Pastré, 1999; Le Boterf, 2018) settings manifest through a dual process where, on the one hand, academic knowledge transforms into action to structure practice, and on the other hand, field experience feeds and recontextualises formal knowledge. This mode of operation takes place within the framework of a prolific back-and-forth between practice and theory.

In this movement, the disciplinary breakdown of Coulet and Loisy (2018) is central. By establishing a program logic, co-constructing the training offer, ensuring continuity between teaching units, it ensures curricular coherence and allows for interdisciplinarity. Moreover, this breakdown allows academic production to align more closely with the operational needs on the ground, offering learners training whose relevance and content updates are guaranteed.

Beyond the academic and professional aspects of this competence dynamic, a socio-economic dimension is also recognised in a transversality that gives competence a civic and territorial purpose through its contribution to local development and living together in various economic sectors where tacit know-how and theoretical knowledge intersect. Therefore, the influence of this approach is important for all stakeholders in the professionalisation of training.

Indeed, universities are required to implement modern and professional training programs. For educational policies, they are required to ensure a collaborative setup of these programs by bringing together economic operators and research professors. As for the students, the opportunity offered to them is to ensure courses that develop their reflexivity, innovation, as well as their adaptation to various complex situations. In light of these virtues, transversality and disciplinary decompartmentalization emerge as levers to ensure, at the end of the training, output profiles with versatile skills that promote reflexivity and societal engagement.

Figure No. 1: The process of transversality and decompartmentalization

2.6. The axes of transversality for an articulation between university education and professional requirements

The confrontation of the dimensions of professional competence and the academic dimension reveals axes of transversality and decompartmentalization (**Figure No. 02**) necessary for a closer alignment between training and the world of work. The axis related to the ability to mobilise and integrate advocates for the use of all knowledge accepted in a professional context (Minet, 1999; Fernagu-Oudet, 2004) and in the context of initial or continuous training (Coulet, 2011) in authentic and complex situations. In this sense, this transposition of theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and knowledge gained from experience in environments outside the usual ones will take learning out of the isolation of knowledge towards a more operational and transferable one. This vision highlights the transfer and adaptability that can be ensured by "the structuring and [the] mobilisation of knowledge in a manner adequate to the action to be carried out" (Minet, 1995, p. 174). This refers to the ability to adapt one's knowledge to the specificities of the field, in connection with the transfer between situations (Pastré, 1999) and the academic/professional transfer (Coulet, 2011). From this perspective, breaking down barriers translates into the ability to reinvest one's knowledge in new situations, which is a fundamental issue for employability and innovation.

To capitalise on these various transfers, one must move away from the idea that experience alone cannot be formative and that it can only become so within the framework of reflexivity and continuous learning that translate lived actions into learning objects (Le Boterf, 2018; Fernagu-Oudet, 2004). In other words, transversality involves being able to step back from one's own actions in order to analyse, explain, and understand one's practices (Minet, 1995; Pastré, 1999). The idea behind this cognitive analysis is to "systematise experience" (Fernagu-Oudet, 2004; Le Boterf, 2018) by identifying invariants, conceptualising action strategies, and preparing for their transfer to new situations. It is thus a continuous development and professionalisation rather than a simple performance. To ensure this continuous professionalisation in harmony with the field of university education, it is necessary to establish a progressive and contextualised construction of skills. This is possible within the framework of adapting learning to the needs of a professional field as required by "the core of competence" (Minet, 1995, p.133) and situationality (Le

Boterf, 2018). For the context of university training, this progressive construction of skills (Coulet, 2011) must be done through intermediate levels, each corresponding to a higher degree of integration and regulation. In light of these principles that underpin this axis of progressive construction, compartmentalisation occurs at the level of the progressive development of skills, taking into account the duration of the training and the properties of the application contexts.

In this vein, training engineering is better suited to implement this type of desegregation by relating principles related to cross-professionalization (Fernagu-Oudet, 2004), on-the-job training (Pastré, 1999), and the co-construction of training offerings between teacher-researchers and socio-professional stakeholders through a program-based approach (Coulet and Loisy, 2018). The breaking down of barriers within the framework of these foundations concerns the development of relevant, up-to-date, and operational pedagogical devices.

This collaborative construction of training can only be understood if it is guided by its social and professional purposes, which lie at the intersection of the effectiveness of action in work situations (Le Boterf, 2018), the context of the use of competence (Rey, 2015), and the educational and civic purposes related to local development and living together (Gendron, 2019). Transversality is therefore putting skills at the service of multiple purposes: employability, local development, citizenship, social inclusion. In this relationship between skills and goals, breaking down barriers is aimed at a societal and ethical perspective beyond the goal of professional integration.

Transversal Axes	Dimensions of Competence in the Professional Context	Dimensions of Competence in the University Context	Points of Decompartmentalization (Criteria)
Mobilization and integration of knowledge	Integrated mobilization of formalized knowledge for action in complex and real-life situations (Minet, 1999; Fernagu-Oudet, 2004)	Mobilization of formalized knowledge from initial and continuing education (Coulet, 2011)	Ability to contextualize, transfer, and integrate knowledge into action (Minet, 1999)
Transfer and adaptability	Ability to reinvest acquired knowledge in new and unforeseen situations	Transfer between academic training and the professional environment (Coulet, 2011)	Decompartmentalization through linking acquired knowledge with new uses and contexts, fostering employability and innovation
Reflexivity and systematization of experience	Analysis of practices to identify operative invariants and action strategies; intelligence of action (Le Boterf, 2018; Fernagu-Oudet, 2004)	Construction of competences through a reflexive approach to learning experiences transformed into objects of knowledge (Minet, 1999; Pastré, 1999)	Decompartmentalization through reflexivity aimed at continuous professional development
Progressive and contextualized construction of competences	Identification of core competences adapted to professional needs and contextualization of knowledge (Minet, 1999; Le Boterf, 2018)	Adoption of a coherent progression within training programs (Coulet, 2011)	Adoption of a progressive and integrated approach to competence development over the duration of training and across contexts of application
Cross-professionalization and co-construction	Integration of needs and constraints of the world of work (Fernagu-Oudet, 2004; Pastré, 1999)	Pedagogical engineering, program-based approach, collaboration between teachers-researchers and professionals (Loisy, 2018)	Decompartmentalization through the co-construction of updated and operational pedagogical arrangements
Social and civic purposes	Competences oriented toward work effectiveness, local development, citizenship, and social inclusion (Le Boterf, 2018; Gendron, 2019)	Development of critical thinking, civic engagement, and intellectual emancipation (Rey, 2015)	Decompartmentalization through a societal and ethical perspective that goes beyond employability alone

Figure No. 02: Transversalities to be observed in the context of bringing the French degree programme (CPND-LLE-2020–2021) closer to the Nomenclature of Craft Activities and Trades (MPME & A, 2007).

3. THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to identify areas of transversality between university programs and the artisanal field, a cross-content analysis between the French bachelor's program (National Pedagogical Council of the Arts and Foreign Languages Domain (CPND-LLE-2020-2021) and the Nomenclature of Artisanal Activities and Trades (NAAM) (Ministry of Small and Medium Enterprises and Crafts, 2008) is adopted, following a synthesised approach based on the works of Bardin (1997), Robert and Bouillaguet (2007), and Sabourin (2009).

3.1. Presentation of the analysed documents

The first step is to familiarise oneself with the two documents to be analysed in order to understand their organisation as well as their content (Sabourin, 2009). These are closely related to the official French degree program (now D1), which is organised into teaching units, modules, content, and educational objectives (Figure No. 2), and linked to the nomenclature of artisanal activities and trades (now D2), which includes codes, titles, definitions, and skills of artisanal activity (Figure No. 3).

For D1, it is a French language bachelor's degree program that falls within the field of Letters and Foreign Languages (LLE), revised by the CPND-LLE and implemented starting from the 2020-2021 academic year. The aim of this revision is to update the content to adapt it to societal changes. The recommended content reconciles disciplinary learning (linguistic, literary, civilisational), methodological, and cross-curricular learning related to new technologies, foreign languages, and employability. The training is structured into 06 semesters representing three progressive levels.

Semesters 1 and 2 (S1 & S2) allow for the acquisition of basic communication skills (oral and written comprehension and expression, grammar), disciplinary skills (linguistics, literature, phonetics), and methodological skills (University Work Techniques (ITU), Text Reading and Study (LET), ICT and e-Learning) (**Figure No. 03**). Semesters 3 and 4 (S3 & S4) are the places for continuing the acquisition of communication and disciplinary skills, with new introductions related to the literature of the language. The acquisition also continues for the methodological units with a new integration related to digital literacy. As for the discovery and cross-curricular units, they continue to teach civilisation and foreign languages.

Having reached the third year, the student enters the specialisation phase (S5 & S6) in linguistics, literature (theories and practices), civilisation and interculturality, and becomes familiar with didactics and specialised languages. He will also delve into research methodology and practice reading and writing through workshops dedicated to this purpose. In transversal units, he receives instruction in translation and entrepreneurship.

Semester	Type of UE	Modules	Semester	Type of UE	Modules
S1	UEP	CEE1, CEE1, Grammaire 1, Linguistique & Phonétique 1, Literary Text 1	S3	UEP	CEE3, CEE3, Grammaire 3, Linguistique & Phonétique 3, Literary 3
	UEM	TTU1, LET1, ICT & E-learning		UEM	TTU3, LET3, Digital Literacies 3
	UED	Civilization 1		UED	Civilization 3
	UEF	Foreign Language 1		UEF	Foreign Language 3
S2	UEP	CEE2, CEE2, Grammaire 2, Linguistique & Phonétique 2, Literary Text 2	S4	UEP	CEE4, CEE4, Grammaire 4, Linguistique & Phonétique 4, Literary 4
	UEM	TTU2, LET2		UEM	TTU4, LET4, Digital Literacies 4
	UED	Civilization 2		UED	Civilization 4
	UEF	Foreign Language 2		UEF	Foreign Language 4
S5	UEP	Linguistics 1, Literature, Theories & Practices 1, Civilization 1, Interculturality 1, Introduction to Didactics 1, Languages for Specific Purposes 1	S6	UEP	Linguistics 2, Literature, Theories & Practices 2, Civilization 2, Interculturality 2, Introduction to Didactics 2, Languages for Specific Purposes 2
	UEM	Research Methodology 1, Reading/Writing Workshop 1, Oral Communication 1		UEM	Research Methodology 2, Reading/Writing Workshop 2, Oral Communication 2
	UED	Translation 1		UED	Translation 2
	UEF	Entrepreneurship 1		UEF	Entrepreneurship 2

Figure No. 3: Structure of the French Bachelor's Degree (CPND-LLE-2020-2021)

Regarding the D2, it concerns the Nomenclature of Craft Activities and Trades (NAAM)¹. This revised classification comes in a context of statutory, technological, and economic changes as well as changes in professions and offers artisans a legal and organisational framework that guides and situates their activity. For decision-makers, it allows them to manage the national file, coordinate intervention actions by the authorities, as well as collect data (statistics and other information) related to the sector for potential decision-making. It should be noted that this nomenclature is divided into three main areas related to crafts and art crafts bearing code no. 1, with goods production crafts (code no. 02) as well as service crafts (code no. 3). The identification of activities is done using a 07-digit code. The reading of this code reveals that the first two digits concern the field (01, 02, 03), the next two refer to the sector (from 01 to 24), and the last three digits designate the specific activity (from 001 to 999) (Figure No. 4). This system of identifying artisanal activities works towards an intelligible reading of the nomenclature as well as ease of updating it according to contextual developments.

Nomenclature of Handicrafts and Trades (Algeria)	
01. Handicrafts and Artistic Crafts	
Sectors: Food, Clay/Stone/Glass, Metals, Wood, Wool, Fabric, Leather, Miscellaneous Materials	
02. Production Handicrafts	
Sectors: Mining/Quarrying, Mechanics/Electricity, Metallurgy, Food, Textiles/Leather, Wood/Furniture, Construction/Building Materials, Jewellery, Miscellaneous Goods	
03. Service Handicrafts	
Sectors: Installation/Maintenance, Repair/Upkeep, Mechanical Works, Interior Design/Decoration, Hygiene, Clothing, Miscellaneous Services	
Codification: - 2 digits = Domain (01, 02, 03) - 2 digits = Sector (01-24) - 3 digits = Activity (001-999) Example: 02 18 004 → Domain II, Sector 18, Activity 004	

Figure No. 4: Structuring of the Nomenclature of Craft Activities and Trades (MPME&A, 2007)

3.2. The method and analysis technique

The analysis approach first consisted of a comprehensive reading and segmentation of the two documents (D1 and D2) in order to extract the most relevant units of meaning, namely the modules that represent the blocks of knowledge and pedagogical activities for D1 (CPND-LLE, 2020-2021) and the job sheets (the 7-digit identification code, identification and title of the artisanal profession, the description of the main activity, the content of the activity, the accessory activities) (NAAM, 2007) that allow for the observation of the professional skills associated with these sheets for D2.

¹Nomenclature promulgated on 31 October 2007 by Executive Decree No. 07-339, as an update to the initial text related to Executive Decree No. 97-140 of 30 April 1997. <https://www.mta.gov.dz/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/NOMENCLATURE-FR.pdf>

The first segmentation and coding aim to identify academic knowledge (SA) (from D1) and action knowledge (SAct) (from D2) as a basis for comparison in order to identify convergences, complementarities, and discrepancies that may exist between university education and artisanal professions.

The knowledge in question was identified using more detailed indicators drawn from Fernagu-Oudet (2004) classification of knowledge and related to the pedagogical objectives, content, and proposed activities for D1. The intersection between the two types of knowledge (Minet, 1995; Fernagu-Oudet, 2004) resulted in the grid below (**Figure No. 5**).

Author / Model(Minet, 1995)	Dimension(Minet, 1995)	Types of Knowledge(Fernagu-Oudet, 2004)	Indicators
Minet (1995)	Formalized Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Theoretical or scientific knowledge - Procedural knowledge applied to operations - Codified knowledge 	Existence of written references, theoretical frameworks, and procedures that can be formalized (to understand, interpret, reason, analyze, know-how).
Minet (1995)	Knowledge in Action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experiential knowledge - Implicit, tacit knowledge - Procedural knowledge embedded in action - Knowledge in use 	Presence of knowledge arising from experience or practice; non-formalized, often implicit, enabling action, adaptation, decision-making, strategy, and practical know-how.
Minet (1995)	Situated Mobilization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge specific to a given context - Knowledge derived from practice, learned through action 	Ability to activate knowledge and skills in a complex situation that requires diagnosing, characterizing, and transferring.
Minet (1995)	Transformation of Activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge acquired through experience and practice - Knowledge learned by doing 	Adaptability and evolution of competencies through reflective experiences and learning processes.
Minet (1995)	Contextual Core of Competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contextualized knowledge - Experiential knowledge (craftsman/artisan) - Relational knowledge 	Articulation of contextualized knowledge and operational know-how (doing, acting); collective mobilization and shared practices.

Figure No. 5: Classification of knowledge according to Minet (1995) in light of the types of knowledge according to Fernagu-Oudet (2004)

The analysed units were subject to a second cross-thematic coding based on a grid structured around six axes (integrated mobilisation of knowledge, transfer and adaptability, reflexivity and continuous learning, progressive construction and contextualisation, training engineering and co-construction, social and professional purpose), allowing each block of knowledge from the Bachelor's degree to be matched with one or more artisanal trades identified by the nomenclature codes. This connection led to the extraction of concrete examples of transferable pedagogical activities and corresponding professional tasks, organised in cross-tables associating modules, transversal skills, professions, and illustrations. The qualitative analysis resulting from this framework allowed for the identification of convergences, gaps, and transferability potential between academic content and professional requirements, followed by the proposal of an interpretative synthesis structured by a transversal axis. This approach thus provides a detailed reading of the areas of separation between university education and craftsmanship and opens up perspectives for pedagogical adaptation aimed at strengthening the transversality and relevance of the CPND-LLE Bachelor's degree in light of the needs of the artisanal sector.

3.2.1. Sampling

For the identification and analysis of action knowledge (SAct) derived from the Nomenclature of Craft Activities and Trades (NAAM, 2007), the methodological choice did not focus on the exhaustiveness of the 338 listed trades, but on a reasoned and representative sampling, in accordance with the principles of qualitative content analysis (Bardin, 1997; Sabourin, 2009). This sampling was defined based on explicit criteria: sectoral representativeness, socio-economic weight of activities, heritage and cultural value of

certain trades, as well as their relevance in relation to the skills developed in university language programs (communication, translation, documentation, mediation, promotion of products and know-how) (**Figure No. 6**). On this basis, several strategic sectors were selected in the three areas of craftsmanship (traditional and artistic, production of goods, services), notably food, textiles and leather, wood and artistic craftsmanship, artisanal communication, and services related to clothing and maintenance. For each of these sectors, two to three professions were selected, forming a corpus of about twelve to fifteen job descriptions, allowing for a detailed and contextualised analysis of the knowledge of action.

Each job description was analysed based on its normative structure (seven-digit code, title, main activity, content, and ancillary activities) in order to identify the knowledge mobilised, the recurring professional gestures, and the social purposes of the action. These skills were then related to the academic knowledge of the CPND-LLE Bachelor's degree (D1) through a double coding, by type of knowledge (Minet, 1995; Fernagu-Oudet, 2004) and according to the six transversal axes (AX1 to AX6). This mapping allowed for the establishment of explicit links between university pedagogical activities and artisanal professional tasks. The results, organised in cross-tabulations, served as the basis for an interpretive analysis highlighting areas of transversality, the logic of breaking down barriers between training and profession, as well as the levers of pedagogical adaptation that strengthen the professionalising scope of the French Bachelor's degree in the face of the realities of the artisanal sector.

Artisanal domain	Sector (NAAM)	Occupation code	Title of artisanal occupation	Main activity
Domain 01: Traditional and artistic craftsmanship	Food	01-01-001	Olive oil refiner	Artisanal extraction and processing of oil
	Food	01-01-004	Traditional pastry maker	Preparation / artisanal processing
	Food	01-01-003	Traditional couscous maker	Preparation / artisanal processing
	Earth and fire	01-02-005	Potter	Shaping and firing of clay items
	Earth and fire	01-02-007	Ceramicist	Manufacture / decoration and firing of ceramics
	Metals / stone	01-03-002	Artistic blacksmith	Metalwork (shaping, assembling, finishing)
	Metals / stone	01-03-007	Traditional jeweler	Manufacture and finishing of jewelry
	Metals / stone	01-03-008	Stone carver	Cutting, shaping and assembling stone
	Traditional textile	01-05-004	Traditional carpet maker	Weaving and assembling carpets
	Traditional textile	01-06-001	Embroiderer	Decorative embroidery and textile finishing
Leather / artistic craftsmanship	01-07-002	Artistic leatherworker	Cutting, sewing and finishing leather objects	
Domain 02: Craft production of goods	Wood	02-14-003	Artistic cabinetmaker	Design and manufacture of wooden furniture
	Textile / clothing	02-13-005	Tailor	Garment making and fitting
	Agro-food	02-12-003	Baker-pastry chef	Artisanal food production (preparation, baking, control)
	Parts / manufacturing	02-10-002	Spare-parts manufacturer	Fabrication, machining and assembly of parts
	Construction	02-15-004	Mason	Construction, assembly and finishing of structures
	Metal / boiler-making	02-11-003	Boilermaker	Metal shaping, assembly and welding
	Jewelry (production)	02-16-001	Jeweler	Manufacture, adjustment and quality control
Domain 03: Craft services	Clothing services	03-23-002	Alterations tailor	Fitting, alterations and customization
	Maintenance	03-20-001	Custom mechanic	Repair, adjustment and mechanical maintenance
	Industrial equipment	03-18-001	Industrial equipment installer	Installation, setup and commissioning
	Diagnostics / maintenance	03-19-002	Diagnostic technician	Fault diagnosis and troubleshooting
	Miscellaneous services	03-24-001	Artisanal service provider	Multi-skilled technical interventions (maintenance/assistance)

Figure No. 6: Sample of artisanal occupations analyzed for the identification of action-based knowledge (NAAM, 2007)

4. PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

4.1. The dynamics of the construction of formalised knowledge: between theories, methods, and reasoning

The relationship between the types of knowledge (Minet, 1995; Fernagu-Oudet, 2004) with the pedagogical objectives, content, and activities offered in the French degree program shows the presence of three types of knowledge related to theoretical, scientific, or scholarly knowledge, procedural or operational knowledge, as well as cognitive knowledge. These types of knowledge are respectively identifiable for theoretical knowledge through verbs such as understand, define, identify concepts, through verbs such as write, apply, structure, or produce for procedural or operational knowledge, as well as through verbs such as analyse, reason, understand, or interpret for cognitive knowledge.

Their permanent articulation in the French degree program (CPND-LLE, 2020-2021) is evident in all the modules of semesters 1 and 2. This is the case for the “Reading Comprehension and Written Expression 1 (CEE1)” module, which addresses textual typologies with a particular focus on the descriptive type and its macrostructure (at the textual level) and its microstructure (at the paragraph level). Once this theoretical knowledge has been addressed, its practical application is carried out through the development of strategies for constructing the literal and inferential meaning of a descriptive text, as well as through the production of this same type of text. This complementarity between written comprehension and written production converges with the objective that aims to lead the student to produce coherent texts.

This objective is pursued within the framework of the “Reading Comprehension and Written Expression 2 (CEE2)” module only with another textual typology related to narrative text and story writing, which reflects a progression towards more complex textual genres.

These textual genres cannot exist outside the contexts of their production, which is why the “Oral Comprehension and Expression (CEO1)” module aims to guide students in expressing themselves in “different communication situations.” To do this, it is essential to draw on theoretical knowledge related to “types of discourse and communication situations,” procedural knowledge that can be embodied in “oral presentations and role-playing,” as well as cognitive knowledge for the development of students' reflexivity. These can be mobilised in the context of note-taking and comprehension.

To solidify the students' abilities in production and expression (both oral and written), theoretical knowledge related to the study of grammatical categories and syntactic functions is introduced within the framework of the Grammar module (1 & 2), which aims to guide students to “distinguish between the grammatical nature and syntactic function of words.” This objective also encourages the implementation of procedural knowledge related to morphological and syntactic analysis, as well as cognitive knowledge essential for reasoning about sentence structure. These three types of knowledge unfold in an intertwining manner at the level of the “Linguistics-Phonetics (1 & 2)” module, which offers theoretical knowledge related to Saussurian concepts (sign, syntagmatic axes, paradigmatic axes, etc.), procedural knowledge that puts them into practice through transcription exercises, as well as cognitive knowledge consisting of developing observation and interpretation skills through corpus analysis. In the same vein of articulating theory, practice, and reflection, the “University Work Techniques (ITU1 & 2)” module presents itself as a privileged space for the deployment of procedural knowledge within the framework of a transversal learning approach around note-taking, preparing presentations or summaries, and organising work. These practical activities are underpinned by theoretical knowledge drawn from research methodology and call upon cognitive skills such as synthesis and organisation of ideas. All of this knowledge is a testament to the perspective given to this teaching, which aims to “equip students with the necessary methodological tools to conduct research.”

The objective of equipping students with various tools is also at the heart of the modules “Study of Literary Texts (1 & 2)” and “Reading and Text Study (1&2)” which focus on an

association between theory and practice by providing students with both theoretical knowledge about literary text (genre, register, narration) and about text in general (textual analysis and understanding of paratext) as well as procedural knowledge (l) to ensure a methodical and analytical reading of a text as well as the identification of discursive cues. All of this knowledge allows for the development of cognitive skills related to interpretation and critical reasoning of various texts, with a focus on literary texts. In the wake of these textual typologies, the Civilisation (1-2) module extends learning on the structures and components of texts towards their cultural and civilisational dimensions by addressing concepts of culture, values, and French and Francophone institutions. The aim pursued is to develop capacities for understanding and critically analysing cultural phenomena.

In order to integrate all the knowledge provided through these modules into their current context and to underpin them with essential knowledge for their learning, procedural knowledge related to the mastery of digital tools (PowerPoint, Excel, Word, digital platforms) is provided within the framework of the “ICT and E-learning” module. This subject also provides a space for the application of theoretical knowledge regarding the use of digital technology in teaching and learning as a vector of cognitive knowledge mobilised within the framework of research and word processing.

4.2. An evolution towards a consolidation and acquisition of more reflective and critical knowledge

The content analysis of semesters 3 and 4 shows a content organisation that aims to consolidate the knowledge covered in the previous semesters and to move towards a more reflective and critical acquisition of knowledge. This new orientation, observed through the classification of knowledge advocated by Minet (1995) (theoretical, procedural, and cognitive) as well as through the notions of praxic knowledge (knowing how to reflect on one's own practice by characterising it, diagnosing it, transferring it, etc.) and professionalisation engineering (Fernagu-Oudet, 2004), adopts an upward progression that tends to orient training towards a conceptualisation of action (Pastré, 1999). This conceptualisation allows for a break from the compartmentalisation of knowledge in order to integrate them into an operational logic that focusses on integration and mobilisation in action.

This logic is manifested through the way theoretical, procedural, and cognitive knowledge is integrated into the second year of the bachelor's program. For theoretical knowledge, structured at the level of fundamental units (grammar, linguistics, literature, and civilisation), they function as tools for analysis and interpretation to the extent that they transform from abstract knowledge into knowledge that can be mobilised in action situations. This is the case for grammar, which becomes contrastive, for linguistics, which finds applications in corpus research, and for civilisation, which, through its content, offers possibilities for critical and intercultural reading.

As for procedural knowledge, it materialises in terms of concrete tasks through speaking in simulation situations (CEE/CEO teaching units), argumentative writing, research projects (TTU teaching unit), and digital tools (LN teaching unit). Thus, these tasks reflect an evolution of knowledge towards its operational and procedural aspects, which should allow students to move beyond reproduction activities towards autonomous achievements. This orientation is clearly displayed through the following objectives: “produce a coherent text,” “organise a presentation,” “use digital tools for research and communication.” As for cognitive knowledge, it is present through tasks that require problematization, comparison, contextualisation, and critique of texts. The teaching unit “Reading and Text Study” concretises these tasks through a critical reading of texts aimed at developing skills in interpretation and historical and cultural contextualisation. As for the teaching unit “Literatures of the Language of Study,” it allows for the implementation of tasks involving

comparison and critique of textual genres. Thus, these tasks, which work towards reflective acquisition and student autonomy, converge with knowledge related to information processing, reasoning, and analysis (Fernagu-Oudet, 2004) that perfectly reflect a thought model based on “the internalisation of intellectual action patterns.” This model should also ensure the transferability of the skills targeted by the second year of the French bachelor's degree.

This objective of skill transferability is supported by a harmonious progression between the knowledge of semester 3 and semester 4. These integrate conceptual, technical, and methodological dimensions within the framework of projects that students will combine in order to produce well-argued dossiers within the framework of the University Work Technique (TT4) teaching unit or to analyse linguistic corpora within the framework of the “Linguistics and Phonetics” teaching units. This integration approach, which implements processes of conceptual mastery, analysis, and critical reasoning, perfectly aligns with the conceptualisation of action (Pastré, 1999) where knowledge is operational, integrated, and transformative rather than juxtaposed.

In light of this analysis, the second year witnesses a transition from formalised knowledge to operational knowledge that finds applications not only in academic situations but also in professional ones, as is the case in the artisanal sector where the transfer of communication, analysis, planning, and critical thinking skills is possible.

4.3. From theoretical knowledge to procedural knowledge: towards a conceptualisation of action and progressive professionalisation

The perspective of gradually transforming theoretical knowledge into operational knowledge continues in the third year (S5 & S6) within the framework of an ascending progression that heralds the conceptualisation of action and a coherent and gradual professionalisation. This evolutionary logic of the two aspects of the articulation of undergraduate training with its professional context is present in the teaching units of semesters 5 and 6 through the combination of theoretical, procedural, and cognitive knowledge in favour of their mobilisation, transfer, and integration into action.

This process towards the conceptualisation of action and gradual professionalisation is based on the theoretical knowledge present in the teaching units of the third year of the bachelor's degree as a starting point for their transformation into operational knowledge. These are disciplinary knowledge related to linguistic, cultural, and educational facts, the intelligibility of which ensures their mobilisation in action. In this vein, tools are provided to students through the “Linguistics” and “Literature” UEs, which respectively equip students with models for language description at various levels (syntactic, semantic, and discursive) and for the analysis and critique of literary texts.

The teachings related to civilisation are considered as meeting points of the cultural and historical dimensions of the Francophone sphere. As for the knowledge imparted in didactics, it concerns the pedagogical foundations of teaching directly related to the pedagogical alignment ensured by the coherence between objectives, teaching approaches, and evaluation. As for the teaching units related to specialised languages, they focus on the concepts of FOS, FLP, and FOU, as the conceptual foundation of professional communication. All this knowledge from semester 5 will pave the way in semester 6 for a transformation of knowledge into procedural knowledge, in other words, into operational modes and methodical approaches.

This conceptual consolidation paves the way, in the sixth semester, for a transformation of knowledge into procedural knowledge, that is, into operational modes and methodical approaches. This is the case for the “Didactics” module where students are led to develop action plans through the creation of teaching sequences that include objectives, tasks, and evaluation criteria. The same goes for the “Linguistics” module where the transition from

conceptual to operational is manifested through the use of quantitative and qualitative analysis methods as well as through the creation of written, oral, and digital corpora. In specialised language, the writing of technical texts, popular summaries, or terminological sheets illustrates the transfer to professional practices (linguistic mediation, sectoral communication).

Professional practices are also called upon through pragmatic skills to be developed via writing and oral expression modules, as well as through complex tasks such as summary notes, debates, or professional pitches, which serve as excellent venues for implementing know-how. The perspective of transitioning from theoretical knowledge to practical skills is manifested through the "Entrepreneurship" module, which promotes the creation and presentation of concrete projects, thereby bringing the training closer to the socio-economic environment.

4.4. The knowledge of action in the Nomenclature of Craft Activities and Professions

4.4.1. The knowledge of action and artisanal dynamics in field 01: Traditional and artistic crafts

The implementation of the classification of action knowledge as advocated by Minet (1995) reveals that in the field of traditional crafts and art (01), food processing professions rely on technical (procedural) knowledge that is inherent to the nature of the professional activity and is characterised by its codification, as is the case for the professions of traditional cake maker (01-01-004) and couscous maker (01-01-003) or oil refiner (01-01-001). In the context of these professions, knowledge of preparation and transformation is put into practice in combination with scientific knowledge related to dosages, seasonal periods, as well as local practices. The association of procedural knowledge (techniques) with theoretical and environmental knowledge related to the observation of materials and production conditions is raised in the context of earth and fire crafts (potter (01-02-005), ceramicist (01-02-007), and stonemason (01-03-008)). Metalworking professions such as artistic blacksmith (01-03-002) and traditional jeweller (01-03-007) also involve procedural knowledge that requires highly specialised technical operations (welding, polishing, setting, etc.) as well as empirical knowledge related to aesthetics and symbolism. This order of knowledge (experiential) is present in the professions of carpet maker (01-05-004), embroiderer (01-06-001), and art leatherworker (01-07-002) which, in addition to the technical gestures specific to the professions (knotting, embroidering, cutting, sewing), require actions related to the adaptation, adjustment, or regulation of patterns, colours, finishes, and shapes to local characteristics and practices.

All the aforementioned professions thus rely on action-based knowledge that articulates standardised technical gestures, situated professional skills, as well as cultural anchors, contributing to the transmission and preservation of heritage as well as the strengthening of social cohesion. This gives these professions a very strong identity dimension through social and relational knowledge (the symbolism of jewellery, festive cakes, decorative festive calligraphy, etc.).

The knowledge invoked within the framework of the aforementioned professions lies in several cross-cutting areas specific to the field of crafts and art (01) and which refer to technical cross-cutting (transformation and mastery of materials), cultural cross-cutting (symbolism and ancestral heritage), identity and social cross-cutting (collective), and patrimonial cross-cutting (restoration of tangible and intangible heritage).

4.4.2. The knowledge of action and productive technical skills in field 02: Craftsmanship in the production of goods

Unlike the field of traditional and artistic craftsmanship (01) characterised by traditional production techniques, the field of goods production craftsmanship (02) relies on

procedural knowledge supported by more industrialised techniques. These procedural skills, combined with experiential, environmental, contextual, and relational knowledge, involve various operations specific to several trades in this field (spare parts manufacturer, cabinetmaker, mason, jeweller, coppersmith, tailor-dressmaker).

However, there are common cores of techniques and operations grouped into families. The first core of these operations concerns the transformation of matter, which is at the heart of artisanal activity. The modifications made to the raw material concern stone, metal, wood, textile, dough, and are based on operations of extraction, shaping, machining, kneading, cutting, or moulding. These controlled operations contribute to the shaping of the material from a functional, usage, and value-added perspective. Other common operations occur in the trades related to the production of goods and involve assembly and shaping. These operations involve connecting elements, securing them within the framework of the jeweller and coppersmith professions, as well as adjusting them for the tailor-dressmaker profession.

These trades also intersect within a third core of operations related to adjustment, precision, and fine-tuning, which work towards their compliance with the demands of the professions and the quality of their products. The control of dosages in pastry (02-12-003), the precision of settings in jewellery (02-16-001), the adjustment of clothing (02-13-005) and sheet metal (02-11-003) reflect a desire to correct, refine, and stabilise professional gestures according to the achieved results.

In addition to these precision operations, other operations come into play in the aforementioned trades, which, in addition to their functional nature, ensure the conformity of the products to social requirements by guaranteeing their graceful aesthetics as well as their durability. These are the finishing and quality control operations, embodied by the couturier's touch-ups, the mason's finishes, the baking control in bakery-pastry, as well as the polishing and chiselling in jewellery.

All the operations mentioned in this section overlap in terms of compliance with standards and procedures (technical, sanitary, safety, and productive) that ensure the longevity of the product and the trust of its users. It is true that each of the trades cited as examples within this field of the art of goods production develops actions in favour of quality productivity, but it can only be guaranteed by respecting the reliability and traceability of the action, whether it is related to compliance with safety standards in the workshop or on the construction site, or with the control of production stages, or with the conformity of assembled or welded elements.

The operations identified within the framework of this second area of craftsmanship constitute a core of transversal skills that demonstrate the transferable nature of action knowledge among the crafts and the possibility of cross-professionalization from a common operational base. It is also important to emphasise the fundamental role of experiential, environmental, and relational knowledge, which work in favour of the quality and loyalty of products through various actions of adjustment, contextualisation, as well as adaptation to the material, human, and normative requirements of the sector.

4.4.3. Action knowledge and professional versatility in field 03: Service crafts

The field of service crafts is no exception when it comes to the transversal action knowledge mobilised by the professions within this sector of activities.

This common base of technical operations includes, as a set of operational invariants, (Minet, 1995) installation, assembly, and commissioning operations that generally ensure the immediate functionality of the devices in question. To do this, several actions are carried out and involve machining and mechanical adjustment techniques in relation to well-defined requests (custom mechanic, 03-20-001), as well as the installation, assembly, and adjustment of industrial equipment (industrial equipment installer, 03-18-001), and the

implementation of materials with specific characteristics as particular service provisions (miscellaneous service provider, 03-24-001).

The operations of diagnosis, repair, and maintenance also appear as a second invariant that involves operations of fault diagnosis or malfunction analysis (03-19-002, 03-20-100, and 03-18-001), intervention on technical installations to repair the fault or change the part, and the return to service of the equipment.

The operations common to the trades in the field of service craftsmanship refer to maintenance, cleaning, and prevention operations that involve codified technical operations of cleaning, disinfection, and health control in various contexts (collective, domestic, and industrial). These operations also exist in other forms in activities where there is regular maintenance, restoration, and strict compliance with standards and safety, as is the case with the job of a miscellaneous service provider (03-24-001).

Other types of operational invariants bring together trades in the field of service crafts (03) and primarily cover operations of adjustment, retouching, and personalisation. These fall within the same line of personalisation and technical intervention. This is the case for the professions of tailor (03-23-002) and decorative plasterer (03-23-002), which involve adjustment and adaptation operations but on different objects. For the tailor, it is about adapting clothing to the needs of clients, whether it concerns morphology or clothing usage. As for the artisan mason-plasterer decorator, they are required to make adjustments and finishes according to the characteristics and architectural styles of the buildings. All the aforementioned trades are subject to control, verification, and compliance operations that ensure the satisfaction of the needs expressed by clients and guarantee the reliability of the action and the sustainability of the interventions carried out.

Thus, despite the diversity of professions, they intersect at the level of transversal skill cores characterised by effective intervention in various situations, adaptability, and flexibility, giving these professions a social and economic grounding as well as a central role in solving community problems.

4.5. Transversality between university education and the Nomenclature of Craft Activities and Trades

4.5.1. Mobilisation and integration of knowledge

The intersection of the formalised knowledge from the French degree (D1) with the action-based knowledge from the artisanal field (D2) at the level of axis 1 “mobilisation and integration of knowledge” highlights a very strong operational convergence in the construction of competence. Whether it falls under the field of education or that of craftsmanship, it is established not through the accumulation of knowledge, but through its transformation into resources that can be mobilised and integrated into authentic situations. As observed in the analysis of craft professions as well as in the knowledge blocks of the bachelor's degree, procedural and experiential knowledge is activated in response to technical, material, and social constraints. This principle of knowledge mobilisation is similar at the S1 and S2 levels of the bachelor's degree and more particularly in the CEE/CEO, Grammar, Text Studies, and TTU modules where students apply linguistic and grammatical knowledge in language action tasks such as writing, document analysis, transcription, or presentations. The use of artisanal materials (job sheets, technical notices, descriptions of professional gestures, or presentations of artisanal products) thus allows linguistic learning to be situated in situations close to professional action and makes language a tool for formalising activity.

This articulation of knowledge is reinforced in semesters S3 and S4, when the modules on corpus analysis, linguistics, methodology, or civilisation adopt a more interpretive and reflective stance. The study of narratives of artisanal experience, justifications of professional practices, or technical texts allows students to understand how an actor

justifies, corrects, and adapts their actions in the face of constraints or unforeseen events, following a logic analogous to that of the artisan at work. Environmental and contextual knowledge (local resources, rules, social customs) is also extended through the analysis of situated discourses and contextualised professional practices, while relational and communicational knowledge is enhanced through simulations of artisan-client communication, professional writing, or collective projects.

Finally, in semesters S5 and S6, devices such as the design of didactic sequences, the analysis of specialised corpora, or entrepreneurial projects place students in a complex situation of jointly mobilising theoretical, methodological, and practical knowledge, echoing the simultaneous mobilisation of different registers of knowledge in artisanal action. Thus, the “Mobilisation and Integration of Knowledge” axis reveals a real breakdown of barriers between the French Bachelor's degree and craftsmanship, demonstrating that language can be conceived as an instrument of action, mediation, and professionalisation (Minet, 1995; Pastré, 1999; Fernagu-Oudet, 2004).

4.5.2. Transfer and adaptability

A functional continuity between the skills acquired during a French degree and the professional activities in the three fields of craftsmanship is highlighted at the transversal axis “Transfer and adaptability.” This extension between the two sectors (training and professional) is noticeable in the analytical skills acquired during the study of literary, discursive, and specialised texts and linguistic corpora, as well as in the analysis of complex professional situations. In craftsmanship, this skill is demonstrated by the ability to identify and interpret concrete problems (breakdown, manufacturing defect, special order, organisational constraint). Similarly, the abilities to contextualise and interpret linguistic usages, developed in modules on textual analysis, linguistics, or civilisation, can be applied using artisanal materials (descriptions of practices, professional testimonies, technical documents) to understand the material, environmental, and sociocultural constraints of intervention contexts. Thus, the transfer occurs from the text to the professional situation, with the ability to analyse and contextualise resources being central to adapting to various work environments.

This transfer is reinforced by the writing, argumentative, and communication skills developed during the Bachelor's program. The exercises in synthesis, commentary, argumentative production, and oral presentations directly prepare for the writing of professional documents related to craftsmanship (technical sheets, explanatory notices, instructions, product presentations, customer communication materials). The reasoned debates, academic pitches, and FOS/FOU writings are related to simulated artisanal situations (negotiation, service presentation, promotion of a local product), and the methodological skills acquired in the TTU and academic projects are transferred to the facilitation of workshops, construction sites, or services. Finally, in S5 and S6, the resolution of complex and open tasks develops a mental flexibility comparable to that of the artisan, who must adapt to new materials, techniques, or constraints. The design of action and the anticipation of new requirements, developed at the university, then align with Pastré's (1999) action schemes, with transfer and adaptability becoming tools for breaking down barriers between university education and artisanal practices, serving the employability and professionalisation of graduates.

4.5.3. Reflexivity and systematisation of experience

The bachelor's degree in French and the crafts in the three fields of craftsmanship are closely correlated at the transversal axis of “reflexivity and systematisation of experience.” The implementation of reflexivity in the field of craftsmanship allows for the development and refinement of competence within an iterative process of observation, action analysis, and adjustment from a perspective of awareness of the impact of the interventions carried

out and their regulation. The goal pursued is to deduce operational invariants or an intelligence of action (Le Boterf, 2018; Pastré, 1999). Concomitantly, analytical reflexivity is deployed in French undergraduate training through text study, clarification of reasoning, and justification of reasoning and methodological and linguistic decisions.

The use of artisanal materials - experience narratives, descriptions of professional gestures, justifications of practices, or artisanal case studies - thus allows students to exercise their diagnostic, interpretive, and analytical skills on real-world action situations, the first element of breaking down the barriers between academic training and the professional world.

This cross-cutting nature is consolidated when university education exposes students to practices of conceptualisation and systematisation of experience. During semesters S3 and S4, the modules dedicated to critical reading, corpus analysis, and methodology lead students to identify regularities, develop practice models, and build praxic knowledge (Fernagu-Oudet, 2004), in accordance with artisanal practices of anticipation, adjustment, and adaptation to material or contextual constraints.

In semesters 5 and 6, approaches such as the design of didactic sequences, qualitative and quantitative corpus analysis, the development of professional documents, or the implementation of entrepreneurial projects lead students to conceptualise their practice and transform the university experience into transferable operational schemes. This dynamic converges with that of the expert craftsman who is able to formalise their experience in order to improve their practices, personalise their interventions, and transfer their expertise to new situations. Reflexivity and the systematisation of experience, therefore, constitute a common professionalisation mechanism for both the Bachelor's degree and craftsmanship, sustainably strengthening the link between university education and professional activity.

4.5.4. Progressive and contextualised construction of skills

The analysis of the transversal axis related to the progressive and contextualised construction of skills highlights a significant convergence between the professionalisation dynamics observed within the French Bachelor's program (CPND-LLE) and those characteristic of the three domains of craftsmanship. In manual trades, learning occurs through internalisation and repetition of the gesture, then through gradual adaptation to the properties of materials, technical constraints, and social norms. The same logic drives the Bachelor's degree, where, from semesters 1 and 2, basic theoretical knowledge (textual typologies, linguistic concepts, grammatical structures) is applied in simple tasks (writing, transcription, text comprehension).

The use of resources from the artisanal field, such as descriptions of professional gestures, technical documents, and job sheets, allows for anchoring linguistic learning in concrete action situations, thus demonstrating that, in both contexts, competence develops gradually and through levels of increasing complexity.

This gradual elaboration is associated with a process of contextualisation and conversion of knowledge into operational schemes. In the field of craftsmanship, technical practices take on meaning when they are adapted to the characteristics of materials, safety regulations, environmental requirements, or social conventions; this logic is also evident in the Bachelor's program, in semesters S3 and S4, through comparative analyses, contextualised corpus studies, methodological projects, or the use of digital tools applied to professional contexts, including those related to craftsmanship. In the third year (semesters five and six), pedagogical devices, including the design of didactic sequences, the writing of professional documents, the qualitative and quantitative analysis of corpora, and the implementation of entrepreneurial projects, confront students with the need to conceptualise their actions, anticipate changes in requirements, and adapt their practices, much like the expert craftsman who individualises their interventions and creates in the face of constraints.

Consequently, the gradual and contextualised development of skills proves to be a common organising principle for both fields, which justifies breaking down the barriers between university education and the artisanal sector, and confirms that professionalisation is based on the rooting of knowledge and its contextualised application in action.

4.5.5. Cross-professionalization and co-construction

The approach focused on cross-professionalization and co-construction highlights a structural convergence between the acquisition of skills provided by the French Bachelor's degree and the professional trajectories observed in the three sectors of craftsmanship. In manual professions, competence is acquired through immersion, repetition, and adjustment of gestures according to the material and the situation: the chiselling of a jewel, the modelling of clay, the adjustment of a mechanical part, or the diagnosis of a breakdown only gain professional value through the gradual stabilisation of experience. An analogous logic supports the Bachelor's curriculum from the very first semesters S1 and S2, during which students become familiar with fundamental theoretical knowledge (textual typologies, linguistic notions, grammatical structures), knowledge that they apply in simple but contextualised tasks (writing descriptive texts, phonetic transcription, document analysis).

The use of artisanal materials, such as descriptions of professional gestures, technical documents, and job sheets, helps to anchor linguistic learning in situations similar to professional activity, thus confirming that competence, in both contexts considered, develops gradually and over the long term.

This gradual development is based on a continuous co-construction between formalised knowledge and practical knowledge. In the artisanal production of goods, mastery of machining, welding, or moulding relies exclusively on adaptation to materials, safety standards, and site constraints; similarly, at the L2 and L3 levels (semesters 3 to 6), students combine disciplinary, procedural, and practical knowledge in increasingly complex projects. Corpus studies, methodological projects, specialised writings (terminology, popularisation, technical texts), didactic sequences, or entrepreneurial projects place students in a position analogous to that of the expert craftsman, who personalises their interventions, innovates in the face of difficulties, and adjusts their practices to social or professional requirements. The academic progression, moving from theory to conceptualised action, thus converges with the artisanal logic, characterised by a controlled and subsequently adapted gesture, with professionalisation transforming into a co-construction process. The latter is based on the continuous integration of knowledge and its transformation into contextualised modes of action, ensuring real permeability between university education and artisanal practices.

4.5.6. Social and civic purposes

The examination of the transversal axis of social and civic purposes highlights a fundamental convergence between the university education provided within the framework of the French Bachelor's degree (CPND-LLE) and the professional practices observed in the three sectors of craftsmanship. In the field of craftsmanship, the activity is intrinsically orientated towards social utility and service to the community, notably through the preservation of cultural and intangible heritage in traditional and artistic craftsmanship, the contribution to housing, food, and security in the production of goods, as well as meeting the daily needs of the population in service craftsmanship, including hygiene, repair, maintenance, and assistance. These practices root craftsmanship in a logic of proximity, solidarity, and local development. The integration of this field into the Bachelor's curriculum can be achieved through the analysis of texts related to artisanal trades, through projects documenting local heritage, as well as through written and oral productions highlighting regional skills, thereby consolidating the social anchoring of linguistic learning.

Furthermore, university citizenship is emphasised by the French Bachelor's degree (CPND-LLE) through foundations related to critical thinking, knowledge of sociocultural issues, as well as ethical responsibility. The courses in linguistics, literature, civilisation, methodology, and didactics lead students to question discourses, contextualise values, and understand cultural diversity, while the modules in university work techniques (ITU) and entrepreneurship promote the development of skills in organisation, communication, and teamwork. The permeability between the academic environment and the artisanal sector is evident when these skills are mobilised for socially-oriented situations, such as writing communication materials for artisans, linguistic mediation in local cultural projects, the written and digital enhancement of artisanal heritage, as well as the design of territorial entrepreneurship projects. As a result, the "Social and Civic Purposes" axis highlights that professionalisation goes beyond merely acquiring disciplinary skills, fitting into a broader societal perspective, aiming to train responsible, inclusive, and supportive actors, working in service of the community and local development.

5. CONCLUSION

This research started from the idea of bringing language training closer to the socio-professional environment through a case study in the artisanal field. This adequacy was considered based on the identification of transversalities that could ensure the breaking down of the questioned training. Faced with this objective, this research started from the main assumption that the transfer of skills from training to professional environments and vice versa is only possible through the identification of core competencies through an association between formalised knowledge (theoretical, procedural, and cognitive) and action knowledge (procedural, experiential, environmental, etc.) within the framework of situated and reflective learning devices. A second underlying hypothesis assumes that this intersection is only possible through six transversalities that make up the observation grid of this association. The transversalities of mobilization/integration, transfer/adaptability, reflexivity/systematization, progressive construction/contextualization, co-professionalization/co-construction, social and civic purposes were implemented using a qualitative content analysis to demonstrate the actional nature of the language through operations of formalisation, explanation, mediation, argumentation, and support for professional activity. The segmentation of the content of the French degree and the Algerian Nomenclature of Craft Activities, their dual coding by types of knowledge and by axes, as well as the reasoned sampling of a corpus of crafts from three areas of craftsmanship (01.02.03), highlighted blocks of content from the French degree training and professional tasks that reveal operational convergences.

These operational convergences, which globally validate the initial hypotheses, show the emergence of cross-cutting skill cores related to communication/mediation (oral/written), planning and organisation (methodology, task management), analysis and diagnosis (text/corpus alongside manufacturing problems, defects, breakdowns), reflexivity and regulation (explicitation, justification with the aim of continuous improvement), and adaptability and contextualisation (recontextualising acquired knowledge in training in parallel with the artisanal world, codified material, technical, and social constraints). Thus, the assumption of transfer is confirmed to the extent that the methodological and linguistic skills emanating from the French degree program can be transposed into the field of craftsmanship through artisanal supports such as instructions, job sheets, experience narratives, and descriptions of gestures. These supports serve as a means of didactic mediation, and language thus becomes a tool for formalising action and enhancing skills. Areas of decompartmentalization as well as gaps were also highlighted by the grid of the

six transversal axes. It highlights the unequal nature of transferability depending on the professions (variable weight of standards, technicality, and environments) and according to pedagogical conditions (partnerships, task scripting, support, and aligned evaluation).

These results could be expanded if limitations had not arisen within the framework of this research. These limitations stem from the very nature of the analysed documents (D1/D2), which do not allow for statistical generalisation. Other limitations arise and concern the lack of direct observation of ongoing or workshop practices in addition to empirical data from artisans and students through interviews, observations, and experimentation with devices.

Despite these limitations, the contributions of this research lie in establishing a transferable analysis framework that allows for reflections on desegregated professionalisation through an articulation between formalised knowledge and action-based knowledge, and through the identification of concrete entry points for curricular adaptation (mediation tasks, professional writings, authentic materials, territorial projects, simulations).

In order to address the aforementioned limitations and concretise the considerable contributions of this research in the field, it is necessary to broaden perspectives towards an empirical validation of the analysis models developed within the framework of this article through empirical studies, and to co-construct pedagogical devices in close collaboration between the university and the craft sector. Their implementation is guaranteed through partnerships between the two sectors, by adopting the program-based approach as well as by establishing field internship projects. The perspectives also concern the integration of digital technology as a space for transversality through catalogues, heritage storytelling, and online mediation, as well as the expansion to other language training and economic sectors in order to strengthen a professionalisation engineering that ensures the employability of graduates and their territorial and civic anchoring.

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